

The value of anthropology and the concept of culture in professional training for the strengthening of democracy in Colombia

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The loss of humanities in university education is a threat to democracy. Professionals who are not trained in the humanities lack the tools for critical reflection and recognition of difference. Based on an exercise of reflection on teaching experience and literature review, this article establishes the importance of training in the humanities, particularly anthropology, in higher education. The text highlights the dangers for democracy that arise when the humanities are suppressed from professional training. In addition, the concept of culture is used as a justification for the relevance of anthropology and its knowledge in the recognition of difference, the denaturalization of lifestyles and science, and the understanding of the other. The reflection concludes that all these possibilities offered by the concept of culture are central to the defense of democracy.

Keywords: Anthropology, Culture, Vocational training, Strengthening democracy.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The loss of humanities in university education is a threat to democracy. Professionals who are not trained in the humanities lack the tools for critical reflection and recognition of difference. This context leads to the question: what tools and knowledge does a student need to be a professional in any area of knowledge? From an anthropological perspective, not only is training in techniques and knowledge key, but it is also necessary to build a reflective perspective oriented towards thinking.

Hence the importance of humanistic training in university education. From a reflective perspective, this text mentions the difficulties and relevance of university teaching of the humanities, particularly anthropology. The main scenario from which the reflection is constructed is the teaching experience. In the university context from which this reflective writing starts, anthropology is taught to students in the areas of health, engineering, psychology, cinema, criminalistics, and sports. There are many barriers faced by professors when educating students who do not see anthropology as a central, relevant, or useful disciplinary knowledge.

Among the obstacles to humanistic education is the transformation of the university itself in the 21st century. The new university, conceived from the perspective of the knowledge society, has ended up favoring technical and disciplinary knowledge in specific fields of the basic sciences - which account for current market situations - to respond to problems identified quickly and efficiently. In this process, the time for reflection and analysis to which the humanities are accustomed to thinking about the risks, assumptions, or biases of any project or research is reduced to a minimum. In this way, transformations in the curricula and knowledge proper to the humanities are left on the sidelines and lagging behind the needs and challenges of society or the market.

In this context, the years of teaching on which this reflection is based allow us to construct approaches that respond to the questions that guide this text: What is the current teaching context of the humanities? What are the difficulties faced by teachers in the teaching of the humanities? What is the importance of anthropology training in Higher Education? How is the concept of culture central to demonstrating the relevance of anthropology in professional training?

Apart from the introduction, this reflective article is divided into two parts. The first reflects on the context of teaching the humanities at the university level. Then, it argues about the importance of teaching anthropology in higher education. To do so, it resorts to the concept of culture as a key category that accounts for the relevance of anthropological knowledge for students of non-humanistic disciplines.

2. REFLECTIONS ON THE EDUCATIONAL CONTEXT AND THE CHALLENGES OF TEACHING THE HUMANITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Teaching humanities subjects in the university context is becoming increasingly difficult. Among some students from areas other than the humanities, there is an imaginary that these classes are filler. This idea has been reinforced by the paradigms of education for work, a model that is more technical than humanistic. The question "What good is this going to do me?" is recurrent among students. It is not easy to demonstrate to them the relevance and pertinence of humanistic education. All this situation adds to the frustration of teachers due to the students' lack of reflexivity, critical capacity, or reading level. Their low skills make it more difficult to teach in any area, but in the humanities, it becomes more complex because their uselessness is assumed.

The current context of humanities education also has a curricular dimension. The reduction of academic programs from 10 to 8 semesters is a response to the idea of a contemporary university in line with the Bologna agreement [1]. In this exercise, humanities subjects are generally eliminated because they are considered surplus, filler, or less relevant to professional training. On the other hand, the curricula of various degree programs sometimes contemplate the humanities generically. Classes called Humanities I or Sociohumanistics are common. The lack of a disciplinary approach makes the teaching of the humanities more complex, as the content lacks depth. It is paradoxical, and at the same time very telling, that there are

humanities classes with these names, while those of basic sciences are not called, for example, Basic I, but Physics, Calculus, Chemistry, etc. Why are disciplines such as chemistry, physics, and biology considered basic and not sociology, history, anthropology, or philosophy? In many curricula, grids, or curricular structures, the humanities are thought of as part of complementary or accessory training. It is assumed that humanistic areas are on the margins of disciplinary training and not at its base.

For this reason, one of the great paradoxes of this whole problem is that it seems to contradict what was agreed in the Bologna agreement of 1999. There, the idea of a knowledge society is enshrined, and technical, patent and applied knowledge is privileged. This knowledge society could lead us to think that we are facing an era based on philosophical reflection for knowledge; but, in reality, what it seeks is to select the types of knowledge required for the training of professionals to respond to technical and productive challenges, which does not give room to the humanities.

Higher education in Colombia has faced significant challenges in the integration of the humanities into the curricula, despite their importance in the formation of human beings. The humanities play an essential role in education, as they contribute to the development of critical thinking, analytical skills, and cultural sensitivity [2]. More profoundly, some authors mention that the teaching of humanities has to do with human dignity:

The purpose of the humanities is to dignify the human and that of education is to form integral beings, being the humanities the ones in charge of articulating and giving social meaning to knowledge. Therefore, to vindicate the humanities, in general, presupposes the inclusion of a particular form of human dignity. Not to do so is to legitimize all forms of violence manifested in our society [3].

However, the general perspective is that the humanities are in crisis [2]. A *silent crisis* as it is called [4]. In recent years, there has been a growing trend towards greater specialization and emphasis on the development of technical and professional skills, to the detriment of humanistic areas. This utilitarian vision of education has relegated the humanities to the background, questioning their relevance and pertinence in the current context [5]. [6] point out that this situation can generate a fragmented and unbalanced education, favoring the development of instrumental competencies over those of a humanistic and axiological nature. And this is demonstrated by the perspective of students who ask themselves: *Why do I have to watch these classes, if they are just filler?* [6]. The question implicitly carries the utilitarian idea with which education has been thought in its neoliberal perspective related to efficiency.

At risk is the development of imagination, creativity, and critical thinking, he says [4], but what worries him most is that democracy is also at risk. An education that only trains people who know how to be useful to the economy, who stop questioning and end up legitimizing injustices, inequalities, and violence: *Nations around the world will soon be producing generations of useful machines, instead of complete citizens who can think for themselves, criticize tradition and understand the meaning of other people's sufferings and achievements* [4]. In the same vein [5], he mentions that the current idea of development that is based on innovation and economic growth has modified the university to such an extent that it no longer reflects on whether there are other possible ways of being.

The humanities, not being in this line, have become knowledge of lesser importance and are therefore being excluded. In addition, such a scenario has led to the humanities gradually losing funding and decreasing their presence in university training programs [2, 7, 8]. This is undoubtedly related to subsequent decision making at the political level and the quality of professionals graduating from the university.

Another aspect to consider is what some authors refer to as *the society of immediacy*, where an instrumental and pragmatic conception of short-term knowledge prevails [7]. In this scenario, humanistic training takes a secondary place in the face of the demands of the labor market, which requires specific skills and competencies in technical and professional areas. The idea of entering an Internet search engine and getting an immediate answer generates in students a culture of superficiality and short-termism, leaving aside the deep reflection and critical analysis that humanistic areas allow in their intersection with other fields of knowledge.

In the face of this negative context, some authors have also invited other types of complementary reflections. For example, [9] raises the question of how to teach humanities in the most unequal region of the planet (Latin America), alluding to the need to enrich the view of its integration with a social justice perspective. For [9], as for [4], what is at stake is democracy, the formation of citizens capable of understanding the world around them and being able to change it; but this reflection does not only involve students but mainly teachers, who must take up the challenge under this broad and current view. Likewise, a call is made to develop new pedagogical and didactic perspectives for the teaching of humanities, so that they are not seen as a brick or an obligation, but as an opportunity to build more just, equitable and supportive societies [7].

At this juncture, the teaching of anthropology takes on special relevance. Anthropology, as a discipline that studies cultural diversity and the human condition, can provide a critical and reflective view of the social, economic, and political dynamics that shape societies and people's lifestyles. From this perspective, the inclusion of anthropology in higher education contributes to the formation of citizens with a social and ethical conscience, capable of questioning hegemonic models, solving social problems, and imagining fairer and more inclusive alternatives. Likewise, the teaching of anthropology at the university can promote intercultural dialogue, respect for difference, and the valuing of ancestral knowledge and wisdom. In an increasingly globalized and complex world, these competencies are fundamental for the formation of professionals committed to the well-being of their communities.

In conclusion, the teaching of the humanities, and in particular anthropology, constitutes a crucial challenge for higher education in Colombia. It is a matter of vindicating an educational model that values the integral formation of the human being, beyond purely mercantilist interests or technical knowledge.

3. THE IMPORTANCE OF ANTHROPOLOGY AND THE CONCEPT OF CULTURE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

3.1 Revisiting the concept of culture

To rescue the role of the humanities as central knowledge in professional training, we consider it necessary to reflect on the concept of culture. In this way, we seek to show how this category becomes relevant in the humanistic education of students from different areas of knowledge.

Part of the emergence of cultural anthropology is based on the concept of culture. From the 19th century until the 1980s, this concept was the subject of reflection within the discipline. However, current anthropology is not reflected in the category. It is taken for granted, to the point that it is not rethought or discussed much. For example, it is very telling that in the Annual Review of Anthropology, there has not been an issue dedicated to the concept of culture in the last decade.

In the review carried out in Scopus and selected for convenience to achieve representativeness of all Latin American countries and as part of the research project for which this reflection is proposed, in several journals in Latin America and the United States, it is shown that there has been no reflection on the concept of culture in the last decade. By reflection, we mean a commitment to discuss its definition, characteristics, applicability, relevance, or scope.

The journal articles consulted show that the concept of culture is absent. One of the reasons for this absence is that notions such as race, power, gender, interculturality, and social class have taken on greater prominence as explanatory categories of contextualized realities. Although discussions of these issues are based on the concept of culture, it is possible to appreciate that the category has become secondary. Without defending the essentialism of the concepts, since it is recognized that they are historical and changing, it is considered necessary not to take for granted their definition, characteristics, and even their role in the discussion of racial, power, gender, and other issues.

Nor does this position imply ignoring the discussions proposed by postmodern, postcolonial, and decolonial studies which, precisely, seek to revise classical terms to deconstruct them and make visible power relations that always mark the non-European Other as less. In this case, culture, as a global concept, is grounded in

contexts that allow explaining from places, histories, and populations how different societies define themselves [10, 11]. Hence its validity as an explanatory category and the need to rethink the concept constantly. It is essential to ground the category to analyze how it is being used or understood without implying the exclusion of the aforementioned discussions. After all, the illustrative value of the concept is central, as is its capacity to facilitate the understanding of the other categories.

The curricula of professional anthropology programs and cross-cutting areas³ contain subjects or themes in which the concept of culture is directly addressed. Moreover, in anthropology textbooks or introductory books, the category is still very important, to the point that they have one or several chapters devoted to its explanation [12-17]. In these texts, the first chapters are aimed at defining culture and its central role within anthropology.

In some cases, as in [16], the first chapter is devoted to introducing and defining anthropology, and the second to explaining culture. In the case of [15] the first three chapters are oriented to culture. His explanation of what anthropology is links it to the category. In the case of the book *Manual of Cultural Anthropology* by [13], the first chapter defines culture as the object of study of the discipline. For its part, of the 5 sections of the book by [17], the first is devoted to culture.

The concept of culture continues to be the basis for understanding various problems of the world and for the formation of reflective and critical professionals. Recognizing the value of culture justifies training in the humanities. This strengthens the recognition of cultural diversity, and the acceptance of differences and makes citizens critical.

3.2 Denaturalization of culture: Lifestyles and science

Although culture is not something natural, it tends to be presented as such. Hence, we can speak of the naturalization, normalization, and even incorporation of culture. The concept of habitus [18] is relevant to thinking about how culture is incorporated into us to the point that we are not aware of it. It is in such a context that the recurrent phrase the fish does not see the water is useful for understanding cultural normalization.

Two elements call our attention when thinking about the denaturalization of culture about the training of professionals. Firstly, it is considered central to denaturalizing the lifestyle of human beings. Secondly, it is important to reflect on the denaturalization of science in the process of training professionals.

As regards the first, to better understand the process of naturalization of culture, we can resort to several examples. The use of clothing, body accessories, or accents are cultural elements of which human beings are not aware due to their naturalization. Nor are they aware of how the digestive system becomes accustomed to the food supplied to them by the society in which they grow up. After all, culture shapes various aspects of human biology [16].

Enculturation, or endoculturation, is central to the naturalization of culture. This is understood as the conscious or unconscious process of cultural learning, in which an older generation transmits to the younger ones the style of acting and thinking [15]. Enculturation, understood as a programming process [16], generates that culture is seen as normal or expected since the way of thinking and acting is assumed as habitual. The process of learning culture allows people to interpret the world and, within it, the actions of others, in a web of meanings [19]. Thus, the world appears to human beings as something that has a particular meaning.

Anthropology develops a reflection tending to denaturalize or denormalize culture. Denaturalization is understood as a process that demonstrates that the way of thinking, acting, and lifestyle of a population is

³ The transversal areas are departments within the universities that teach courses in the social sciences, languages and natural sciences, aimed at students throughout the university. Their purpose is to form basic competencies in all students regardless of the career they are pursuing.

arbitrary; that is, they should not necessarily be that way. The aim is to show how culture is naturalized, even though it is not natural, or normalized, even though it is not. Thus, denaturalization involves unveiling how the enculturation process has taken place.

The denaturalization of culture is a key contribution of anthropology. Its benefits consist of accepting cultural diversity and understanding how various professional problems may vary depending on the cultural context. It is not possible to assume that all contexts are the same. Acknowledging these differences provides an opening to cultural relativism or historical pluralism [20] and to understanding why embedded cultural practices are a factor to be considered in any process involving work with human beings, regardless of the area of training. In this way, questioning the way societies live is an entry threshold to democratic strengthening, criticism, and reflection.

The teaching of anthropology at the university level contributes to the search for answers to the social problems faced by various professionals. Understanding how culture influences the daily lives of human beings helps to recognize the impact of culture in various aspects. In anthropology classes, students are often asked what is the purpose of the profession they are studying. Next, they are asked if their profession is related to human beings. Both questions are an invitation to think about how culture influences the ways of thinking and acting, the lifestyles, and the daily lives of the people involved in their professional practice. How to intervene in the world, how to solve social problems without a humanistic perspective? This is where training in the humanities, particularly in anthropology and, within this, in the concept of culture, is essential.

To cite an example, healthcare students are asked about a recurring clinical problem today. The conversation leads to the fact that, in general, problems such as hypertension or diabetes are common. The line of argument continues by asking them about the causes of these pathologies. Then, they are challenged to think about how to solve or prevent these health problems. The reflection exercise closes with the need to understand how culture affects health problems in terms of causes, development, and consequences. Although it may seem that this argument is obvious, the elimination of humanities in the curricula shows that this notorious issue is being overlooked.

On the other hand, in the same line of thinking about daily life and the relationship with the other, a recurring theme for reflection is that of cultural diversity. A country like Colombia defines itself as pluriethnic and multicultural to account for the great diversity that exists in the territory. The discussion of the subject is not aimed at making an inventory of the diverse cultures, but rather at putting on the table the idea of interculturality and transculturation as part of what we are and its positive valuation. Countries like Colombia tend to value the external and foreign more than our own. This prevents us from seeing the cultural richness of knowledge, practices, and ways of being and being that allow us to understand that the world can be and is in many ways. This reality is precious within the values of democracy, recognizing others as different in their ways of life, but equal as citizens. The understanding and positive valuation of cultural diversity is the best argument against racism, xenophobia, and other forms of exclusion experienced by certain populations. Thus, the concept of culture and its characteristics are central to the acceptance of cultural differences and, in this way, to the strengthening of democracy.

Regarding the second point, the invitation to the denaturalization of culture is also a door to the denaturalization of science. The development of the Sociology of Knowledge, as a theoretical discipline, has been instrumental in understanding science as a social phenomenon in itself, overcoming the image of the scientist isolated in his laboratory [21]. The social studies of science and technology and the history of science are increasingly relevant fields of knowledge to understand the processes of production of scientific knowledge related to key concepts of culture such as race, class, gender, and power. Without detaching it from its cultural context, knowledge production is increasingly seen as the result of complex interactions between diverse social actors and institutions [23, 24].

In this line, an anthropological perspective of science shows how science responds to cultural and symbolic processes that give it shape and meaning. [22] were among the anthropologists who entered laboratories to investigate how scientific knowledge is constructed. In their research, they show how the supposed objectivity of science hides a web of power relations and negotiation processes between different actors

[23]. That is, they show how people's ways of thinking and living are related to the production of knowledge, understanding that people are also moved by their own or collective interests and that they set personal and social goals.

Anthropology's quintessential critique of debating the limits and connections between nature and culture has also been reflected in the way science and technology are understood as social constructs. A process of humanization of science that allows us to assume a critical stance against the idea of absolute truth or unique solutions [25]. This is one of the reasons why the concept of culture is becoming increasingly relevant. It is essential to train students with the critical capacity to stimulate doubt and rethink assumptions, to question truths that no one questions and to be able to think of new possibilities. The cross-cultural perspective of anthropology stimulates curiosity, imagination, and creativity in knowing that different societies have solved their problems in ways that are different from science, but effective and valid [23, 26]. The point, then, is to understand science as an eminently cultural product, immersed in historical, political, and social processes that have been shaping it.

Cultural diversity and democracy are closely related concepts that have been the subject of study and debate in the field of social and political sciences. On the one hand, cultural diversity implies the recognition and appreciation of the different forms of cultural expression that coexist in a society, which implies a denaturalization of culture and understanding of it as something dynamic and constantly evolving [27]. On the other hand, democracy is based on the principles of equality, participation, and recognition of differences, which implies that cultural diversity should be a central element in the construction of a democratic society [28, 29]. Therefore, revisiting the concept of culture, within the framework of anthropological and humanities university education, is an invitation to strengthen democracy, respect for difference, and recognition of the other, fundamental skills for any professional.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Education is a mechanism of democratic formation and not only an effort to build future workers. The search for an inclusive world or a solution to various social problems passes through the concepts, perspectives, and reflections of the humanities. As the text argues, the humanities contribute to the development of critical thinking, creativity, imagination, and confrontation with our reality, in addition to stimulating curiosity. These skills are fundamental in a world that requires solutions to various problems to improve the lives of human beings. Despite this, the humanities are seen as a filler, a mere complement or ornament in professional training. In some cases, they are even an appendix that can be easily eliminated in the face of any need for curricular adjustment.

The university of the 21st century is being thought of as a dehumanized space that privileges technique over critical thinking. This institution adjusts to the market, which governs its destinies. In this scenario, teaching humanities is becoming increasingly difficult. The subjects of history, sociology, anthropology, and philosophy are fewer and fewer. Although the situation seems discouraging, the reflection made in this paper aims to rescue the role of the humanities in the formation of thinking and critical professionals, who recognize cultural differences and understand science as a historical and cultural product. How to solve problems in the world without the tools to understand them? For this reason, categories such as culture and its associated debates are key when thinking about how a profession constructs alternatives to social problems, how to accept differences, or how to understand the position that each one occupies in the world.

Within the reflection constructed, it can also be concluded that the concept of culture is a category with a great deal of projection. Although anthropology does not talk much about the concept, it is precisely this that has given validity and relevance to the discipline as part of the integral formation. Therefore, a call is made to continue working, both practically and reflectively, on this category. After all, culture stands as a lifeline to the crisis in which the humanities find themselves.

The challenge is no small one for the humanities. Given their current disadvantaged position, these disciplines must seek strategies to make their voice heard. In closing, it is proposed that the humanities

reflect on the present moment and respond to it. This implies rethinking the didactics of the teaching of anthropology, history, sociology, and philosophy. For this reason, it is essential to build points of convergence with other disciplines, so that this interdisciplinary dialogue helps to make the contributions of the humanities more visible. This is not a matter of renunciation, but rather of taking on new scenarios and rethinking the teaching task in a world that, although it rejects the humanities, at the same time eagerly calls for them.

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